

Personality traits and participation in holiday trips for people without and with moderate and severe disabilities

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Abstract:

This study examines the relationship between personality traits (using the Big Five-Factor model, and based on categorization of the traits into five dimensions: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism) and participation and its intensity in holiday trips for German people without and with moderate and severe disabilities. Data from the 2013 and 2019 German Socioeconomic Panel (SOEP) surveys were used. To take into account the particular nature of our dependent variable we have run three different regression models (i.e. binary and ordered probit models for panel data, and a zero-inflated ordered probit model). Overall, openness and extraversion are positively associated with a higher participation in holiday trips, whereas conscientiousness and neuroticism have the opposite result. Although agreeableness has a positive effect on participation, it is only significant in the ordered probit model at the 10% level. However, the positive effect of openness on participation is greater for individuals with moderate and severe disabilities, whereas conscientiousness has a lower negative effect on participation in holiday trips. Public programs and policies for people with different grades of disabilities must consider their personality trait aspects to promote and increase their travel opportunities within the German tourism industry.

Keywords: Personality; Big Five-Factor model; disability; Germany.

Introduction

Participation in leisure activities contributes to improving physical and mental health, and to reducing loneliness and mortality risk (e.g. Michalos and Kahlke 2010; Iwasaki et al., 2015). For people facing painful, stressful and negative life events (e.g. divorce, loss of a child, widowhood, unemployment, or the *onset of disability*), leisure activities can also provide distraction, renewed optimism, a sense of self-identity and social inclusion, and faster recovery (Iwasaki et al., 2015; and Walker et al., 2019). For people with disabilities, leisure and recreational activities can offer rehabilitation, therapeutic and health-care opportunities by creating adequate and accessible environments and programs that help them develop their cognitive abilities and social skills (Darcy, 2002; Pagan, 2012 and 2015; and Darcy et al., 2020). These benefits and intensity of participation also depend

on the different types of disabilities that individuals have (i.e. physical, cognitive, mental health, social relationships, etc.). For example, people who are blind or have visual impairments are more likely to participate in leisure activities than those who have intellectual disabilities (Lord and Patterson, 2008).

In this vein, the United Nation Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities adopted on 13 December 2006 (article 30) and the new European Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030 (chapter 5.5) recognise the right of people with disabilities to enjoy and have equal access and opportunities to justice, education, culture, housing, health services, recreation, *leisure*, sport and *tourism*. Despite the increasing number of people who experience a disability (around 16% of global population (i.e. 1.3 billion people) in 2021 according to the World Health Organization (2022), and growing due to demographic and epidemiological changes) and the strong economic impact of disability travel market (e.g. USD 58.7 billion in the United States of America (ODO, 2020)), people with disabilities are often marginalised and excluded from leisure in general, and from tourism and travel activities in particular (Darcy et al., 2020).

Overall and according to Stephan et al. (2014), the differences detected in the levels of participation and intensity reported by individuals are also a reflection, in part, of “their characteristic way of thinking, feeling, and behaving (pp. 565)”, i.e., their personality traits. According to the American Psychological Association (APA), personality can be defined as “the enduring configuration of characteristics and behaviour that comprises an individual’s unique adjustment to life, including major traits, interests, drives, values, self-concept, abilities, and emotional patterns” (<https://dictionary.apa.org/personality>). For the case of tourism, individuals seek travel destinations that are compatible with their personalities (Aaker, 1997), and around 40-50% of the total variance in desired free-time outcome factors are attributed to their personality (Barnett, 2013). According to Leung

and Law (2010), the study of individuals' personality can help identify and better determine their needs and what they want. Although there is abundant literature on the relationship between personality traits and leisure activities (e.g. Plog, 1974; Kirkcaldy and Furnham, 1991; Frew and Shaw, 1999; Jopp and Hertzog, 2010; Jani, 2014; Stephan et al., 2014; Wilson and Dishman, 2015; Wagner et al., 2016; Verma et al., 2017; Sander et al., 2021; Kuper et al. (2022); and Verman et al., 2023), to our knowledge there is no previous studies that have examined the impact of personality traits of people with moderate and severe disabilities on their participation in holiday trips.

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between personality traits and participation in holiday trips for German individuals without and with disabilities. In particular, we are interested in detecting how people with disabilities with different grades of severity and personality profiles also differ in the likelihood to take part in holiday trips and the frequency of such trips. Namely, we attempt to respond to the question: do all personality dimensions affect participation in holiday trips (and their frequency) in the same way by disability status? To examine and measure individuals' personality dimensions, we have used the Big Five-Factor model (BFF), one of the best-known and widely-used and accepted tool in the field of psychology (e.g. McCrae and Costa, 1997 and 1999). This BFF is based on a hierarchical model with five basic dimensions/domains that summarize other specific facets (McCrae and Costa, 1999; Gosling et al., 2003): openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. According to Jani (2014), the BFF can be used to "further understand tourists and predict their possible travel personality (pp.348)". For our purpose, we have drawn longitudinal data from the German Socioeconomic Panel (SOEP) for the years 2013 and 2019 in which there are available data on both participation in holiday trips and personality traits. After a descriptive analysis, we have run three different regression models (i.e. a Random-effects

(RE) binary probit model, a RE ordered probit model, and a zero-inflated ordered probit (ZIOP) model) to examine the relationship between participation in holiday trips and each Big Five personality trait and disability status.

The main contributions of this study are three-fold. First and as noted earlier, this study fills a significant gap within the existing literature on leisure in general, and tourism in particular. We expect significant effects of personality traits on the likelihood to participate in holiday trips and its frequency/intensity in general, and for people with moderate and severe disabilities in particular. Second, this study also contributes to increasing our knowledge on the concept of “social tourism”, and defined as “all activities, relationships and phenomena in the field of tourism resulting from the inclusion of otherwise disadvantaged and excluded groups in participation in tourism (Minnaert et al. 2012, pp 29)”. This participation has important socio-psychological benefits (e.g. increases in self-esteem, social inclusion, self-confidence and independence) for these low-income groups (e.g. people with disabilities) (McCabe and Qiao, 2020; Minnaert, 2022). In addition, the ageing of the population also contributes to the importance and relevance of this type of studies because of the positive relationship between age and disability prevalence. According to the OECD (2021), around 50% of European individuals aged 65 or over have at least some type of limitation in their daily activities (34% with moderate limitations, and 16% with severe ones). Finally, the results of this study can help policy-makers, managers, stakeholders, travel agencies, tourist operators, caregivers, and rehabilitation professionals to design and develop specific actions, products and services aimed at enhancing participation in tourism activities, and a sense of well-being, self-confidence and social inclusion for people with moderate and severe disabilities.

The remainder of the paper is as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on the relationship between personality traits, leisure activities and holiday trips, as well the main hypotheses of the study. It also includes a subsection dedicated to the literature on the particular case of travellers with disabilities. Section 3 describes the database, variables, and econometric models used in the paper. Section 4 presents the results, whereas section 5 discusses the main findings. Finally, the last section presents the conclusions, provides public policy recommendations, and outlines a set of limitations and future venues for research.

Review of literature and main hypotheses

Big Five-Factor model, leisure activities and holiday trips

The personality trait theories suggest that individual's personality can be examined by measuring a set of different and basic dimensions (Costa and McCrae, 2008). As noted earlier, the most popular, and widely-used model to analyse these personality traits is the Big Five-Factor (BFF) model (Mowen, 2000). This model categorizes personality traits into five dimensions: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism (McCrae and Costa, 1999; Gosling et al., 2003). Openness to experience includes individuals who are imaginative, curious, artistic, independent, creative and insightful (e.g. Barnett, 2006; Jani, 2014). Individuals with high conscientiousness scores are diligent, disciplined, efficient, precise, careful, and with high levels of self-control (e.g. Jani, 2014; Bratton, 2015). Extraversion basically means "sociability", and is high for those people who are cheerful, assertive, talkative, warm and energetic, and a greater capacity to cope with stressful situations (e.g. Watson and Hubbard, 1996). Agreeableness is related to facets such as generosity, altruism, trust, tender-mindedness, and modesty, whereas neuroticism represents anxiety, frustration, irrational thinking, hostility and vulnerability (e.g. DeNeve and Cooper, 1998; Barnet, 2013). Costa and

McCrae (2008) claim that these five factors represent causal influences that have impact on lives of all individuals.

However, the BFF has been criticised as an atheoretical approach (Eysenck, 1992; Block, 2010; Feher and Vernon, 2021), and still in development (DeYoung et al., 2010; Kaufman et al., 2019; Kabigting, 2021). For example, Kabigting (2021) presents a historical review of the evolution of the BFF model, and concludes that it “must embrace other domains of science that are imperative in advancing our understanding of human personality and behaviour necessary for optimal human functioning (pp. 95)”. Furthermore, Block (2010) points out the five factors’ “cloudy” measurement, its inappropriateness for studying early childhood, and the non-conceptual understandings of the five factors. Feher and Vernon (2021) review and compare other alternatives (the “HEXACO model”, the “Supernumerary Personality Inventory (SPI), and the “Dark Tetrad Traits (DTT)”) to the BFF model.

The HEXACO is a six-factor model of personality that adds a new dimension called “honesty-humility” to take into consideration differences in fairness and modesty (Ashton et al., 2004; Lee and Ashton, 2008). In addition, the meaning of the factors “agreeableness” and “emotionality (instead of neuroticism in the BFF)” differs slightly compared to the BFF model (Ashton and Lee, 2007 and 2008). Although the HEXACO and BFF models are highly correlated (between 0.52 and 0.87 according to Gaughan et al. (2012), some studies have found that most of the advantages of the HEXACO model are attributed to the honesty-humility and/or emotionality factors (Ashton and Lee, 2008; Gaughan et al., 2012). On the other hand, the SPI were developed and operationalised by Paunonen (2002), and included 10 personality dimensions (conventionality, seductiveness, manipulativeness, thriftiness, humorousness, integrity, femininity, religiosity, risk-taking, and egotism). Finally, the DTT (an extended version of the Dark

Triad (Paulhus and Williams, 2022)) consists of four negative personality features: Machiavellianism, psychopathy, narcissism, and everyday sadism. This model may be positioned at the negative pole of the HEXACO model (Mededovic and Petrovic, 2015).

Apart from these criticisms, lack of consensus, and alternative models of personality, it is worthwhile mentioning that the BFF “has been used in personality psychology since the early 1990s, has been adopted by many researchers and theorists, and was proven practically useful (Raad and Mlacic (2015), pp.564)”. According to Bainbridge et al. (2022), the BFF model can be used as an organizing framework for most of the stand-alone psychological trait scales. Despite this debate on the theoretical foundations of the BFF model, we have adopted this model due to the fact that most of the previous works on the personality and tourism have followed this model, and thanks to the availability of data on each of the big five factors (e.g. in the SOEP). In addition, we are interested in finding associations between each personality trait and the likelihood to participate in holiday trips by disability status (and not in causal relationships).

Looking at the personality dimensions and leisure activities, Stephan et al. (2014) conclude, using a sample of American and French individuals, that the dimensions extraversion and openness are strongly associated with greater participation scores in diverse leisure activities (e.g. physical and developmental games and social activities). Similar results have been found by Wagner et al. (2016) and Sander et al. (2021). On the other hand, Kirkcaldy and Furnham (1991) find a negative relationship between neuroticism and participation in leisure activities. Conscientiousness has been related to higher levels of physical activities (Wilson and Dishman, 2015), whereas agreeableness has been positively linked to social activities, and negatively to cognitive activities (e.g. Jopp and Hertzog, 2010).

As for travel/tourism activities, the work of Plog (1974) was the first to introduce the psychographic system into tourism literature, which has contributed, for example, to explaining tourist behaviour and motivation, and why some tourism destinations have risen or fallen (Plog, 2001). Within this context, there are many empirical studies in tourism research that have investigated personality traits and its influence on travel/tourism behaviour and decision-making process (e.g. Frew and Shaw, 1999; Jackson et al., 2001; Darcy, 2010; Jani, 2014; Verma et al., 2017; Park and Stangl, 2020; Sander et al., 2021; Kuper, 2022; Šagovnović and Kovačić, 2023; and Verman et al., 2023). For example, Frew and Shaw (1999) find, using data for 500 adult residents of Melbourne, a strong association between personality, gender, and tourism behaviour. Jani (2014) uses data from 360 Korean domestic tourists to investigate the relationship between the BFF and travel personality (identifying 12 travel personalities (i.e. cultural, beach bum, trail trekker, city slicker, athlete, history buff, sight seeker, shopping, boater, family, all things and gamer)). He concludes that travel personalities is linked to high scores in openness include athlete, history buff, shopping, and boater, while those low in that trait include beach bun and family. On the other hand, conscientiousness and agreeableness explain respectively 4 (shopping, family, athlete and gamer) and 3 (boater, family and gamer) differences in travel personalities. Verma et al. (2017) collected data from the 285 tourists' who visited India at central locations (tourist places, hotels, and airports), and found that agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness, and extraversion were positive predictors of intention to visit green hotels, but neuroticism was an insignificant predictor. Verma et al. (2023) conclude that individual's personality becomes the better tool to analyse his/her choices for making a travel plan.

The work of Sander et al. (2021) is quite interesting because also uses data taken from the SOEP (for the years 2005, 2009, 2013 and 2017), and investigates longitudinal

associations between Big Five personality traits and the frequency of six leisure activities (i.e. physical activities, socializing, volunteering, political activity, artistic and musical activity, and going out) for three specific age groups (i.e. young, middle-aged, and older adults). Overall, they conclude that “the leisure activities investigated as well as the overall level of participation are most strongly associated with openness (pp. 30)”. However, they do not analyse neither the leisure activity “holiday trips” nor the particular case of people with disabilities. Kuper et al. (2022) also find, using eleven waves taken from the Longitudinal Internet Studies for the Social Sciences (LISS) panel for the Dutch population, a positive relationship between holiday trips and the dimensions extraversion and openness. Conscientiousness was negatively linked to multiple activities, especially online activities, whereas neuroticism was negatively associated with exercise and holidays. Finally, Šagovnović and Kovačić, S. (2023) investigate the roles of the BFF model plus the dimension “Honesty/Humility” in explaining travel motivation for a sample of 130 respondents in Serbia. They find that, for example, “conscientiousness” and “extraversion” positively affect tourists’ motives for fun and connecting with people, whereas “Honesty/Humility” has the opposite effect.

Despite this previous empirical evidence on the relationship between personality traits and leisure/travel, it is of interest to investigate the convergence or divergence of these results with those obtained for the German case. Furthermore, previous studies (e.g. Diener et al., 2003; Schmitt et al., 2007; Bartram, 2013) have found that personality traits significantly vary geographically because of cultural and societal differences. Based on all these findings from the previous literature on personality, leisure and tourism, we may hypothesize that:

H1: Individuals’ personality traits affect their participation in holiday trips.

According to Diener et al. (2003), people with different personality traits characteristics have different leisure preferences. Although the analysis of people with disabilities as consumers of tourism products and services is relatively recent (Burnett and Baker, 2001; Darcy 2002), there has been an increasing number of empirical studies that have analysed the relationship between tourism and disability (see, for example, Singh et al. (2021) for a review). In general, we find that the tourism industry has been traditionally developed around the needs and requests of people without disabilities (Figueiredo et al., 2012), and has marginalised people with disabilities from buying products (Horner and Swarbrooke, 2004). Recently, Abbate et al. (2022) have published a book (as editors) that carries out an exhaustive and complete revision of the conditions, policies and strategies (from a demand and supply side) to allow people with disabilities to fully enjoy a tourism experience, and thus reaching a “tourism for all”. Within this context, it is also worthwhile mentioning the recent work of Moura et al. (2023) that identifies the main motivations of people with disabilities to participate in tourism activities in Portugal (using semi-structured interviews and a questionnaire). They conclude that the dominant travel motivations are intrinsic or self-determined: pleasure, increased knowledge, escape and relaxation, socializing and closeness to family, autonomy, and competence in order to pursue psychological well-being and personal development. However, we must bear in mind that Moura et al. (2023) use a reduced sample of Portuguese individuals with disabilities (only 348).

The BFF model for the case of people with disabilities can be also linked to the literature on “accessible tourism”. According to Buhalis and Darcy (2010), “accessible tourism is a form of tourism that involves collaborative processes between stakeholders that enables people with access requirements, including mobility, vision, hearing and cognitive dimensions of access, to function independently and with equity and dignity

through the delivery of universally designed tourism products, services and environments (pp. 10-11)". Furthermore, Buhalis and Michopoulou (2011) point out that "the accessibility market cannot be perceived as homogenous, as it entails diverse sub-markets with dissimilar needs and requirements. In addition to demographic, socio-economical, psychographic and behavioural variables, the type and the degree of disablement should be taken into account (pp. 148)". They also mention that the use of "Information Communication Technologies (ICTs)" can help address the particular needs and requirements of people with disabilities and using the "social model of disability" as a framework (as compared to the "medical model of disability" that "reduces disability to impairment, thereby positioning the disability as being the problem of the individual" (Darcy and Buhalis, 2011, pp 41)). In this vein, Michopoulou and Buhalis (2013) identify three important tourism information requirements of people with disabilities: a) the veto principle (i.e. the absolutely minimal prerequisite that allows a person to enter a building or make use of a service), b) the accessibility paths within a destination (to plan a holistic travel experience) and, c) the door-to-door access map (to coordinate travel arrangements from home to travel destination). Michopoulou et al. (2015) conclude that "stakeholder collaboration is a key factor for developing accessible tourism solutions, recognising the value of the market and capitalising on it (pp.186)". However, in many cases each stakeholder is working alone, without any kind of collaboration to share benefits for all parties (Michopoulou et al. (2015)).

However, the existence of intrinsic, environmental, and interactive barriers, negative and hostile attitudes, ignorance of travel agents and industry about the specific needs of people with disabilities, lack of information and suitable communication resources (e.g. assistive technologies), adequate accommodation and transportation options, deficient customer service, and high transport costs have been traditionally mentioned within the

existing literature as the main barriers and constraints faced by people with disabilities within the tourism industry (e.g. Smith, 1987; Shaw and Coles, 2004; Eichhorn et al., 2008; Barnes et al., 2010; Darcy, 2010 and 2011; Cohen et al. 2014). These barriers make the decision-making process more complex and challenging (Blichfeldt and Nicolaisen, 2011). Recently, Rubio-Escuderos et al. (2021) point out the positive impact of social tourism and public funds on the improvement of quality of life of people with disabilities by ensuring their social inclusion and independence. They also mention the need to increase our knowledge on accessible tourism, as well as the design of specific training programs that improve the understanding of people with disabilities' needs. However, they only use qualitative information (25 in-depth interviews with people with reduced mobility) to obtain these conclusions. Finally, Gillovic and McIntosh (2020) have presented a future agenda for more inclusive tourism outcomes for people with disabilities as tourism producers and consumers. They mention as main challenges, for example, the need to “increase their self-representation and participation in decision-making; transform power relations; reimagine tourism places and people; and break down social barriers (pp. 1)”.

According to all these previous empirical results for people with disabilities and their relationship with the leisure and tourism industry, we may hypothesize that:

H2: Personality traits have a statistically different impact on the participation in holiday trips by disability status.

Materials and methods

Sample

In this study, we have used longitudinal data taken from the German Socioeconomic Panel (SOEP, version 36), one of the largest and most representative longitudinal datasets that includes annual information from approximately 11,000 German households (since

1984 onwards) on, for example, living conditions, household composition, labour status, income, education, health status, satisfaction measures, leisure activities, and loneliness (for further information see, for example, Goebel et al. (2019)). This survey is undertaken by “the German Institute for Economic Research, (DIW)”. SOEP is collected on the household- and individual-levels, using face-to-face interviews, and the answers are recorded using computer-assisted personal interviews (CAPI mode) (please, visit <https://www.diw.de/en> for further information on sampling design, sample size, non-response, weighting procedures, etc.). In addition, the risk of survey-related panel attrition in the SOEP is below 5% across all subsamples for waves 1984 to 2020 (Sieger et al., 2022). Schröder et al. (2020) mention that “panel survey data (as the SOEP) are facing increasing competition from administrative panel data (pp. 337)”. Although these administrative datasets usually contain a large number of observations, they have important drawbacks. According to Schröder et al. (2020), the accessibility to these administrative micro data is not easy (due to legal reasons), and the information is restricted to administrative purpose; data do not cover all population (this is particularly true for the German case), or do not include information on key variables (e.g. leisure activities, household composition, individuals’ personality, and working hours). On the contrary, panel surveys (e.g. SOEP) have increased their samples and have covered new topics over time; they have oversampled some sub-populations that are increasing their relevance within society (e.g. immigrants, people with disabilities, etc.); the use of new survey techniques has improved data quality; and finally, these national surveys contribute to the process of consolidation and harmonization in large cross-country datasets. Although there are also other longitudinal surveys in Germany (e.g. the German Ageing Survey, DEAS; The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe,

SHARE), they only include some years or data for a particular group of population (e.g. individuals aged 40 (65) or over).

Although the data on individuals' personality traits are available for some years (i.e. 2005, 2009, 2013, 2017 and 2019), we only use the years 2013 and 2019 due to the fact that the information on participation in holiday trips is missing in the other years (there are data for the year 2017 but the sample size is very limited). Therefore, we have created an unbalanced panel of individuals for these two years in Germany. We have selected a sample consisting of individuals aged 15 or over. After selecting individuals who provide valid data for our key variables (i.e. participation in holiday trips, disability status and personality dimensions), the final sample used in the estimation process contains 39,866 person-year observations (which are 21,885 people without disabilities, 8,575 people with moderate disabilities, and 3,215 people with severe disabilities, each observed on average for 1.3 different years).

Measures

Participation in holiday trips has been obtained from questions about leisure time included in the SOEP. In particular, individuals are asked to answer the following question: *“Please indicate how often you take part in: “Going on an excursion or short trip”*. The possible responses are: daily, at least once per week, at least once per month, seldom or never. In our case, we have merged the first two responses, i.e. *“daily/at least once per week”* (due to the low number of responses to the first option *“daily”* provided by people with moderate/severe disabilities), have recoded all answers (similar to Pagan (2020)), and have created our dependent variable *“holiday trips”* that takes the following values: 0=never, 1=seldom, 2=at least once a month, and 3=daily/at least once per week.

Our key variables measuring the five dimensions/domains related to individuals' personality traits have been obtained from a new 15-item version of the Big Five

Inventory (John et al., 1991), included in the SOEP and validated in other previous studies (e.g. Donnellan and Lucas, 2008). To create our Big 5 variables, i.e. “Openness (O), Conscientiousness (C), Extraversion (E), Agreeableness (A), and Neuroticism (N)”, we have used the responses (wherein we have used 3 items to create each dimension/domain) to the following question: “*People can have many different qualities—some are listed below. You will probably find that some of these descriptions fit you completely and that some do not fit you at all. Others may fit to a certain extent (Please answer on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means “does not describe me at all”, and 7 meaning “describes me perfectly”):*”

I am ...:

- 1) Original, someone who comes up with new ideas (O).
- 2) Someone who values artistic, aesthetic experiences (O).
- 3) Imaginative (O).
- 4) A thorough worker (C).
- 5) Somewhat lazy (C). *Inverted.*
- 6) Effective and efficient in completing tasks (C).
- 7) Communicative, talkative (E).
- 8) Outgoing, sociable (E).
- 9) Reserved (E). *Inverted.*
- 10) Sometimes a bit rude to others (A). *Inverted.*
- 11) Forgiving (A).
- 12) Considerate and kind to others (A).
- 13) A worrier (N).
- 14) Nervous (N).
- 15) Relaxed, able to deal with stress (N). *Inverted.*

Using all these responses, we have calculated the mean values of the three subcomponents/facets that belong to each Big 5, and have obtained the corresponding dimension/domain. For example, the component “*Openness (O)*” is the mean value of the

scores reported by individuals for the first three questions (i.e. 1= Original, someone who comes up with new ideas, 2= Someone who values artistic, aesthetic experiences, and 3= Imaginative). It is also worthwhile mentioning that the scores for questions 5, 9, 10 and 15 have been inverted. Following McCrae and Costa (1994) and Scott and Mowen (2007), we assume that individuals' traits are steady between the SOEP waves 2013 and 2019.

To create our disability measure, we have followed the works of DeLeire (2001), Jones et al. (2006), and Gannon (2005), and have used the following two questions included in the SOEP: “*Do you have a health problem that limits you in normal everyday life? (Yes, severely/Yes, somewhat/No, not at all)*”. Individuals responding “*No, not at all*” are defined as people without disabilities. Those individuals who respond “*Yes, severely*” or “*Yes, somewhat*” are also asked: “*Have you had this health problem for more than half a year? (Yes/No)*”. Those individuals who respond “*No*” to this second question are again considered as people without disabilities, whereas those answering “*Yes*” are defined as people with disabilities. We have to bear in mind that the definition of disability differs across surveys. For the German case, the definition of disability which is used as reference appears in book 9 of the German Social Code (SGB IX), which came into effect on 1 July 2001: “A person is disabled when their bodily functions, mental abilities or mental health deviate, *for more than six months*, from the condition typical for a given age so that participation in society is impaired (Article 2(1), SGB IX)”. We also follow the statistical and operational definition used in the European Health Interview Survey (EHIS) and EU statistics on income and living conditions (EU-SILC).

Following Gannon (2005), it is also possible to differentiate two groups within the latter: a) Those reporting a health problem for more than half a year that *severely* limits their normal daily activities; and b) those who report such a condition but state that it limits them somewhat (i.e. *moderately*). Table 1 shows the construction of our disability

variable by using the responses to the two previous questions and the sub-groups proposed by Gannon (2005). Although our disability variable is based on a self-evaluation (compared to other “objective” definitions of disability, e.g. the medical model of disability focused on individuals’ impairments), Gannon and Munley (2009) point out that “this definition of disability is a standard measure used in many OECD countries –it conforms to the newer social model of disability (Oliver, 1983) whereby disability is seen as a consequence of social, attitudinal and environmental barriers that prevent people from participating in society (pp.42)”. Oliver (1990 and 2013) mentions that the individual model must be abandoned and re-orientated to a framework based on this social model. Apart from many criticisms to the social model of disability, Oliver (2013) concludes that the social model must be viewed as a tool to improve peoples’ lives by identifying and eradicating the disabling barriers that they face.

[Table 1]

Method

To estimate the main determinants of the participation in holiday trips and analyse the contribution of each Big 5 dimension to them, we have run three different regression models (e.g. Pagan (2012) and Boto-Garcia (2022) have previously used some of these econometric models): a) A Random-effects (RE) binary probit model; b) A RE ordered probit model, and c) A zero-inflated ordered probit (ZIOP) model. The first two models (Baltagi, 2005; Greene and Hensher, 2010) have been traditionally used in the existing literature on participation in tourism (or other leisure activities, such as, sports or cultural events), and are well-known within the international researcher community. The RE binary probit model estimates the likelihood to participate in holiday trips (participation *versus* non-participation). This model fits into one of the main goals of the paper, i.e. to

analyse the effect of disability on the participation in holidays trips. The second model, RE ordered probit, allows us to deal with rank-ordered holiday/travel frequency choices. As noted earlier, we have four alternatives: 0=never, 1=seldom, 2=at least once a month, and 3=daily/at least once per week. This model introduces the possibility of taking into account the “intensity/frequency” of the participation in holiday trips within our analysis. The ordered probit assumes “that an underlying continuous propensity function (in our case, the description of participation in holidays) that links each choice alternative exists (pp 4, LaMondia et al., 2014)”. The ZIOP model developed by Harris and Zhao (2007) is also run because it accounts for the potential “*excessive*” number of zero observations. According to Appendix Table A1, 10.8% of the total responses are zeros (i.e. no participation in holiday trips), and even greater for those individuals with moderate and severe disabilities (13.03 and 31.07%, respectively). The ZIOP model is based on the existence of two latent equations (processes) (e.g. Greene, 2008): a) Process 1 (participation *versus* no participation): A probit selection equation, and b) Process 2: (intensity of the participation for those individuals who participate in holiday trips): An ordered probit equation. We have opted for running these three models in order to compare the robustness of our results obtained from each model.

Apart from individual’s disability status and each Big 5 component, we have included the following explanatory variables in all equations, which have been traditionally considered in previous empirical studies: gender (women tend to travel less than males (both in number of trips and total time spending) due mainly to higher levels of intrapersonal constraints compared to men (Elias et al., 2015; Hudson, 2000)), age (and its square) (age can act as an important constraint to taking a holiday because of health concerns and/or financial limitations (Zimmer et al., 1995; Losada et al., 2016)), marital status (e.g. single individuals may have a different maximization of choice as for leisure

than married ones (with less time for leisure) (Thrane, 2000; Lee and Bhargava, 2004)), household size and children in the household (holiday and travel are joint economic decisions that involve all family members (Myers and Moncrief, 1978; Nicolau and Mas, 2005) who are usually willing to have vacation together (Fodness, 1992; Kang and Hsu, 2005)), years of education (persons with a university or college degree are more likely to take part in holiday trips as compared to the lowest educational level (Kang and Hsu, 2005)), having German nationality (previous studies have found differences by nationality (with different cultural backgrounds) on vacation preferences, tourism behaviour, destination and travel purpose (USTTA, 1984; Pizam and Sussmann, 1995; Mykletun et al., 2001; Laesser et al., 2014; and Woodside et al., 2011)), household income (in logarithms) and labour status (financial constraints are strong predictors of travel participation (Alegre et al., 2010 and 2013; Karl et al., 2020), and small changes in income affect the probability of taking a holiday in the same direction (Mergouois and Steur (2003)), and year of interview (to control for the economic cycle). We have also included in all our regressions, interaction terms between disability and each component of Big 5 in order to detect different effects of each personality trait on participation in holiday trips by disability status. All calculations have been made using the statistical package STATA 16.

Results

Descriptive analysis

To start with, Figure 1 shows the levels of participation in holiday trips for people without and with disabilities (moderate *versus* severe). We find that people with disabilities (in particular, those with severe limitations in their daily activities) are less likely to participate in holiday trips as compared to people without disabilities. For example, a total of 35.4% of people with severe disabilities have never participated in holiday trips (15.6%

if the individual has a moderate disability), whereas for their non-disabled counterparts this rate is only 8.6% (i.e. 26.8 percentage points lower). If we aggregate the categories “never” and “seldom”, these rates go up to 70.7 and 80.9% for people with moderate and severe disabilities, respectively (whereas this rate is lower for people without disabilities, 62.1%). On the contrary, we find lower rates of participation among people with disabilities as we look at the categories “monthly” and “daily/weekly”. Only 16.2 and 24.9% of people with a severe or moderate disability are taking part in holiday trips “monthly”, respectively, as compared to the percentage found for people without disabilities (33.1%). As noted earlier, the existence of travel constraints (intrinsic, environmental and interactive barriers according to Smith (1987)) confronted by people with disabilities help explain these differences in terms of participation in holiday trips (Smith, 1987; McKercher et al., 2003; Shaw and Coles, 2004; Yau et al., 2004; Darcy and Dowse, 2013). For example, the existence of high financial restrictions, the need to have caregivers to travel (particularly for people with severe disabilities), and the lack of products and services adapted to their needs are strong barriers to people with disabilities’ access to tourism.

[Figure 1]

Figure 2 presents the mean scores of each dimension by disability status and participation in holiday trips (confidence intervals (95%) are also reported). It also shows the mean scores for the total samples by disability status. Looking at the latter, in general we find significant differences (according to the confidence intervals calculated) in terms of personality traits between people without and with disabilities (and between those with a moderate *versus* severe disability). For example, we detect differences by disability status in the mean scores in the dimensions “openness” (lower scores if the individual has a more limiting disability) and “neuroticism” (higher scores among people with

disabilities, in particular if the disability is severe as compared to people without disabilities). These low scores for people with disabilities in the dimension “openness” may be result of the constraints or disabling environments that people with impairments face in their daily life, restricting or impeding their travel opportunities (and consistent with the social model of disability mentioned earlier).As for the dimension “conscientiousness”, we only find differences for people with severe disabilities (i.e. lower mean scores) as compared to those with moderate disabilities or not disabled. In any case, the mean scores are relatively high for all individuals (disabled or not, and always over 5.5 points). The mean scores in “extraversion” are also lower for people with disabilities (with moderate or severe disabilities) as compared to those found for people without disabilities. Finally, no significant differences are found in “agreeableness” by disability status.

[Figure 2]

Looking at the mean scores taking into account the participation in holiday trips (i.e. never, seldom, monthly, and daily/weekly) for people without and with disabilities, we find (according to the confidence intervals) that people with severe disabilities who have never participated in holiday trips report lower scores of “openness” (3.98), “conscientiousness” (5.56) and “extraversion” (4.46) than people without disabilities (4.13, 5.81, and 4.67, respectively). Moreover, we find significantly lower scores in “conscientiousness” and “extraversion” if we compare people with moderate disabilities (5.7 and 4.52, respectively) and people without disabilities (5.81 and 4.67, respectively). On the contrary, people with disabilities (moderate and severe) who have never participated in holiday trips are more likely to report higher mean scores in “neuroticism” than people without disabilities. For example, the differential between those with a severe (moderate) disability and their non-disabled counterparts is 0.59 (0.45) points.

Econometric analysis

Table 2 shows the econometric results obtained after running our regression models (i.e. a RE binary probit model (1), a RE ordered probit model (2), and a ZIOP model (3)), and outlined in the “Method” section. We have to bear in mind that in the ZIOP model (3) we have two processes: a) “Process 1 (participation *versus* no participation)” using a probit selection model (3A), and b) “Process 2 (intensity of the participation for those individuals who participate)” using an ordered probit model (3B). Table 2 also shows the mean values and standard deviations of the explanatory variables included in the estimation process. Furthermore, Appendix Table A2 presents these mean values and standards deviations by disability status. Overall, we find that, for example, people with disabilities (particularly if they are severely limited in their daily activities) are older, less educated, living in smaller households and with lower presence of children, and have worse employment rates and household incomes as compared to people without disabilities.

First, we find in all estimated models that people with severe disabilities are less likely to participate in holiday trips than people without disabilities (reference group). However, the coefficient on “moderate limited” is not significant at conventional levels in any of our three models. This finding confirms the need to eliminate all barriers and constraints that people with disabilities face when, for example, they look for information to plan a holiday, short-break or even day trips, or when they try to take a bus, train, or plane to get to the destination. It is also necessary to take into account that people with disabilities are a heterogenous group with different needs, motivations, and grades of severity of the disability (Darcy, 2010; Pagan, 2015). To address these barriers, Shaw and Agarwal (2012) point out “the importance of involving people with disabilities in the co-

creation and co-production process of all aspects of the travel experience, including the production, marketing and consumption of holidays (pp.160)".

Looking at the estimation results for "process 2" in the ZIOP model, no significant differences in the intensity of participation in holiday trips have been found by disability status. As for the variables measuring personality traits (Big 5), overall we find similar results in our three regression models. We detect a positive and statistically significant relationship between the dimensions "openness" and "extraversion" and the likelihood to participate in holiday trips, whereas the opposite result is found for "conscientiousness" and "neuroticism". For "agreeableness", the coefficient is positive but only significant at 10% (0.0176) as we run the ordered probit model (2). For those individuals who participate in holiday trips (process 2, ordered probit (3B)), we find that "openness" and "extraversion" have a positive relationship with the intensity of taking part in holiday trips, whereas "neuroticism" has a negative association. By contrast, no significant coefficients were found for "conscientiousness" and "agreeableness".

[Table 2]

Turning to the interaction terms between "disability status" and each dimension/domain included in all models (to test our second hypothesis), in general we find statistically significant differences in the domains "conscientiousness" and "agreeableness" for people with moderate and severe disabilities as compared to those for people without disabilities (reference). For example, the coefficients on "moderated limited*conscientiousness" and "severe limited* conscientiousness" in the binary probit model (1) are both positive and significant at conventional levels (0.0937 and 0.158, respectively). Although the negative association of "conscientiousness" with participation in holiday trips (-0.0792) is partly compensated by the corresponding interaction term (0.0937 and 0.158), they are not strong enough to reduce, for example, the significant

negative effect of having a severe disability on participation in holiday trips (-1.445). Therefore, having a more limiting disability contributes to reducing the negative effect of “conscientiousness” on the likelihood to participate in holiday trips. Similar results are found for the process 1 in the ZIOP model (3A). As for “agreeableness”, we find a negative and significant coefficient on “moderated limited* agreeableness” and “severe limited*agreeableness” in the binary probit model (1), i.e., having a moderate or severe disability reduces the effect of “agreeableness” on the likelihood to participate in holiday trips (-0.0698 and -0.15), respectively. These results are also obtained in the probit selection in the ZIOP model (3A), and in the ordered probit model (2) (except the coefficient on “moderated limited* agreeableness”). Finally, we also detect that the coefficient on “severe limited *neuroticism” is positive and significant in the binary probit model (1) (0.0598), and process 1 in the ZIOP model (3A) (0.0572).

Looking at process 2 in the ZIOP model (3B), we only find that the coefficients on “severe limited*extraversion” (0.0546) and “severe limited*agreeableness” (-0.049) are significant at the 10% level. The results obtained for these two interaction terms are in line with those found in the ordered probit model (2). Apart from those interaction terms mentioned above, we also find in this latter model other significant coefficients in terms of “openness” for people with moderate and severe disabilities (0.0367 and 0.0753, respectively), and “extraversion” for people with severe disabilities (0.0618). As for the remaining explanatory variables included in our models, we find, for example, that the probability to participate in holiday trips is higher for females, older and married people, households with children and higher incomes, full and part-time workers, and those having German nationality. The intensity of this participation among travellers is lower for females, widowed, older and less educated individuals, poorer households, those with children, and people who are working.

Discussion

Overall, our results provide arguments and evidence to incorporate the relationship between personality traits and propensity to participate in holiday trips for all travellers in general (first hypothesis), and travellers with disabilities in particular (second hypothesis) within these studies (e.g. Barnett, 2006; Scott and Mowen, 2007; and Qui et al., 2018). As noted earlier, this participation in holiday trips among people with disabilities can become an important tool and mechanism for increasing their social gatherings, health status, self-esteem, independence and confidence, as well as positively impacting emotions, mood, loneliness, and life satisfaction scores (e.g. Iwasaki and Mannell, 2000; Sirgy et al. 2011; Blichfeldt and Nicolaisen, 2011; and Pagan, 2015 and 2020). However and according to our results, people with severe disabilities are less likely than people without disabilities to participate in holiday trips. This result is consistent with the previous empirical evidence (e.g. Darcy, 2002; Pagan, 2015 and 2020). Moreover, participants/travellers with disabilities (moderately or severely limited in their daily activities) have the same intensity of participation in holiday trips as travellers without disabilities (similar to the work of Pagan (2012)).

Looking at the coefficients on each personality dimension, the results support our first hypothesis, and are in line with those studies found in the existing literature on personality traits and participation in leisure activities (e.g. Kirkcaldy and Furnham, 1991; Lu and Kao, 2009; Stephan et al., 2014; Wagner et al., 2016; and Sander et al., 2021). We have found a positive association of “openness” and “extraversion” with the likelihood to participate in holiday trips and its frequency/intensity. On the contrary, “conscientiousness” and “neuroticism” have a negative relationship with this participation and its intensity (except the coefficient on “conscientiousness” that is not significant at conventional levels in the ZIOP model (3B)). This negative result for the

dimension “conscientiousness” is unexpected, but similar to that found by Sander et al. (2021) who obtained that “at the between-person level, individuals with a higher overall participation in leisure activities are considerably more open and more extraverted, and less conscientious and less neurotic than individuals with lower overall participation (pp.7)”. As for the dimension “neuroticism”, individuals with high neuroticism scores such as, for example, people with severe disabilities (according to Figure 2) are more likely to experience depression, guilt, and frustration, and thus having low self-esteem, poor self-control and somatic complaints (Barnet, 2006).

With regard to interaction terms between “disability status” and each personality dimension, our results show the particular relationship between personality traits and disability status, and they are consistent with those found by Estrada-Lopez et al. (2020). For example, the impact of “conscientiousness” on participation in holiday trips is greater for people with moderate and severe disabilities, whereas for “agreeableness” the opposite result is found. We also find that this group report lower scores of “openness”, “conscientiousness” and “extraversion”, and higher scores of “neuroticism” as compared to their non-disabled counterparts. These low openness scores for people with disabilities are associated with having conservative values, putting routine before variety, being less curious and adventurous, and being practical rather than imaginative (Goldberg, 1993). People with disabilities are more likely to be less assertive, active, optimistic, cheerful and sociable (Goldberg, 1993; Barnet, 2006; Costa and McCrae, 2008).

Conclusions

This study has analysed the relationship between personality traits and the participation in holiday trips by disability status in Germany. Using data from the SOEP for the years 2013 and 2019, we have tested two different hypotheses: a) Individuals’ personality traits affect their participation in holiday trips, and b) The impact of each personality trait on

participation in holiday trips is different by disability status. Our results confirm the first hypothesis and are consistent with the previous literature (e.g. Verma et al., 2017; Sander et al., 2021; Kuper et al., 2022). For example, “openness” and “extraversion” positively influence travel participation, whereas the opposite result is found for “conscientiousness” and “neuroticism”. As for the second hypothesis, we have found a partial support because there are significant differences in the impact of personality traits on participation in holiday trips by disability status but *not* in all dimensions. For example, people with disabilities report lower (higher) scores in the dimensions “openness” and “extraversion” (“neuroticism”) as compared to people without disabilities. According to the existing literature, openness positively influences traveller’s hedonic travel motivation (Do Espiritu Santo et al. , 2016), and predicts leisure experiences that increase the opportunities to learn and grow (Barnett, 2013). Secondly, our results also show that people with different personality characteristics also have different levels of participation (and intensity) in holiday trips. We found that the dimension “conscientiousness” positively affects the participation in holiday trips of people with disabilities (greater if the individual has a severe disability). This dimension also contributes to increasing travellers’ motivations (Šagovnović and Kovačić, 2023). On the other hand, the impact of “agreeableness” on the likelihood to participate in holiday trips is lower for those people having a moderate or severe disability. For people with severe disabilities, we also found a greater impact (positive) of the dimension “extraversion” on the intensity of participation in holiday trips, and the opposite result for “agreeableness”.

From a public policy point of view, these findings suggest that personality and disability status must be taken into account to create, promote and carry out specific programs and policies tailored to people with different grades of disability, with the main goal of increasing their participation in leisure activities. As noted earlier, leisure

activities can provide recovery-oriented outcomes, positive social gatherings, and serve as an excellent antidote to depression (e.g. Davison et al., 2005; Iwasaki et al., 2014). For instance, Faullant et al. (2011) pointed out that the more neurotic travellers were more susceptible to experiencing fear. As a result, they devoted more time to planning and selecting destinations and recreational activities in order to minimize their fears and risks (Jani et al., 2014).

From a practical perspective, our results for people with disabilities may be used by tourism professionals (e.g. managers, stakeholders, travel agencies, tourist operators, etc.) to design and implement specific marketing strategies (e.g. differentiated advertising campaigns by customer segments) and better information systems (e.g. promoting the travel destination as an adequate place in terms of relax, self-fulfilment, security, confidence, familiarity, health care services, accessibility, entertainment, etc.) that consider and suit their personality traits. In addition, new products and services may be designed according to their personalities in order to enhance their tourism experiences. In this vein, Tesin et al. (2023) conclude that the dimension “conscientiousness” (very important for people with disabilities in terms of participation according to our results) positively influences sincerity and satisfaction, whereas “openness” (also a significant dimension in our estimations) affects how much a person is willing to learn and be more informed about the destination (Kovačić et al., 2022). Therefore, tourism industry may incorporate these important two dimensions for people with disabilities in order to increase its knowledge and understanding of their motivations, behaviours, needs and demands. For the case of travellers with disabilities, we should remind ourselves that the size of this market is increasing every year, and is attracting a good deal attention from the tourism industry. For example and according to the report of “The Open Doors Organization” (2020), American adult travellers with disabilities “took a total of 81

million trips and spent \$58.7 billion on just their own travel, up from \$34.6 billion in the prior 2015 study”. In Europe, the World Tourism Organization (2020) estimates that the potential market of people with disabilities is around 80 million people, wherein 70% of them have enough financial resources and physical capabilities to travel, and tend to travel accompanied by 2 or 3 persons (e.g. caregivers, family member, or friends).

Finally, this study presents some limitations. First, the SOEP does not provide any information on the type of disability that the individual has. Although we are controlling for the grade of severity of disability in this study, we would have preferred to have available data on the type of disability (e.g. mental disorders, brain injury, physical limitations, or visual and hearing impairments). Figueiredo et al. (2012) conclude that “the most important aspect determining the level of engagement in tourism and leisure activities is, in fact, the different physical and motor capabilities and the different levels of dependency to move posed by specific impairments (pp. 548)”. Second, the SOEP does not include information on other personality dimensions used in alternative models of personality as, for example, the HEXACO model that adds the dimension “honesty-humility”. Third, we only use data for the German case (e.g. Germany consists of 16 states/landers which differ in terms of population, tourism activities and facilities, history, environments, and even dialects), and this fact limits the generalizability and extension of our findings to other countries. Fourth, we may assume that personality traits may contribute to predicting the onset of disability or health limitations (e.g. Vollrath, 2006), because people with different personalities may react in a different way before, during and after adverse or negative situations (e.g. becoming disabled). As a result, we need additional longitudinal datasets that allow us to follow up on the individuals before, during and after the onset of disability in order to examine how their tourism and leisure preferences and needs change in each phase (i.e. anticipation, onset and adaptation). In

our case, we have used only two waves in the SOEP (2013 and 2019), and thus cannot carry out this type of longitudinal studies. Only new waves in the SOEP or additional datasets can resolve this drawback. Future research could be based on the use of these incoming data, and thus shed further light on the relationship between disability, personality and leisure activities. Moreover, it is important to shed further light on potential gender differences (particularly important for women with disabilities who face a double discrimination based on gender and disability) in terms of participation in leisure activities, as well as how women are more likely than males to report lower or higher scores in each dimension of the BFF model.

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Figure 1. Participation in holiday trips (i.e. never, seldom, at least one a month, and less once a week/daily) by disability status in Germany.

Note: Weighted data. Individual aged 16 or over. *Difference between “people without disabilities” and “people with moderate disabilities” is significant at $P < 0.05$. **Difference between “people without moderate disabilities” and “people with severe disabilities” is significant at $P < 0.05$. Sample sizes: non-disabled= 37,001, moderate limited= 11,977, and severe limited= 4,525.
Source: SOEP for the years 2013 and 2019.

Figure 2. Mean scores for the BIG 5 (i.e. openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism) by participation in holiday trips (i.e. never, seldom, at least one a month, and less once a week/daily) and disability status in Germany.

Note: Weighted data. Individual aged 16 or over. Confidence intervals (95%) are shown. Sample sizes: non-disabled= 28,209, moderate limited= 9,962, and severe limited= 3,743.
Source: SOEP for the years 2013 and 2019.

Table 1. Definition of our disability variable.

Disability status:	<p>Question 1:</p> <p>“Do you have a health problem that limits you in normal everyday life?”</p> <p><i>(Yes, severely/Yes, somewhat/No, not at all)</i></p>	<p>Question 2 (only for those individuals who respond “Yes, severely” or “Yes, somewhat” to question 1):</p> <p>“Have you had this health problem for more than half a year?”</p> <p><i>(Yes, /No)</i></p>
Non-disabled	No, not at all	No
Moderate limited	Yes, somewhat	Yes
Severe limited	Yes, severely	Yes

Table 2. Panel data results from different regression models (binary probit, ordered probit and Zero-inflated ordered probit model, respectively) on participation in holiday trips in Germany.

	Mean (Standard deviation)	Binary probit model	Ordered probit model	ZIOP (3)	
		(1)	(2)	Process 1: Probit selection (3A)	Process 2: Ordered probit (3B)
		<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>	<i>Coeff. (SE)</i>
Disability status					
Non-disabled (<i>reference</i>)	0.665	-	-	-	-
Moderate limited	0.243	-0.261 (0.299)	-0.254 (0.169)	-0.0600 (0.286)	-0.180 (0.168)
Severe limited	0.092	-1.445*** (0.337)	-1.188*** (0.245)	-1.096*** (0.291)	-0.419 (0.263)
Personality traits (Big 5)					
Openness	4,591 (1.194)	0.134*** (0.0182)	0.110*** (0.00831)	0.107*** (0.0191)	0.0797*** (0.00801)
Conscientiousness	5,831 (0.910)	-0.0792*** (0.0241)	-0.0269** (0.0108)	-0.0582** (0.0228)	-0.0165 (0.0103)
Extraversion	4,894 (1.133)	0.0681*** (0.0187)	0.0586*** (0.00852)	0.0418** (0.0183)	0.0493*** (0.00798)
Agreeableness	5,411 (0.965)	0.0309 (0.0219)	0.0176* (0.00980)	0.0234 (0.0213)	0.0105 (0.00939)
Neuroticism	3,639 (1.249)	-0.0747*** (0.0172)	-0.0466*** (0.0079)	-0.0592*** (0.0171)	-0.0291*** (0.0075)
Interaction terms					
Moderate limited * Openness	1.106 (2.043)	0.0294 (0.0292)	0.0367** (0.0156)	0.00377 (0.0284)	0.0124 (0.0158)
Moderate limited * Conscientiousness	1.415 (2.538)	0.0937** (0.0377)	0.0356* (0.0204)	0.0772** (0.0341)	0.00620 (0.0196)
Moderate limited * Extraversion	1.169 (2.137)	-0.0107 (0.0313)	-0.00544 (0.0166)	-0.0114 (0.0303)	-0.00288 (0.0167)
Moderate limited * Agreeableness	1.311 (2.364)	-0.0698** (0.0355)	-0.0248 (0.0189)	-0.0659** (0.0331)	0.00498 (0.0185)
Moderate limited * Neuroticism	0.952 (1.787)	-0.0382 (0.0271)	-0.0188 (0.0145)	-0.0254 (0.0254)	-0.000380 (0.0141)
Severe limited * Openness	0.411 (1.349)	0.0234 (0.0337)	0.0753*** (0.0251)	-0.0114 (0.0303)	0.0184 (0.0271)
Severe limited * Conscientiousness	0.527 (1.685)	0.158*** (0.0413)	0.0904*** (0.0308)	0.117*** (0.0346)	0.00945 (0.0318)
Severe limited * Extraversion	0.435 (1.413)	0.0431 (0.0358)	0.0618** (0.0273)	0.0298 (0.0310)	0.0546* (0.0300)
Severe limited * Agreeableness	0.497 (1.595)	-0.150*** (0.0400)	-0.121*** (0.0291)	-0.0945*** (0.0339)	-0.0490* (0.0294)
Severe limited * Neuroticism	0.392 (1.298)	0.0598* (0.0306)	0.0293 (0.0228)	0.0572** (0.0263)	0.0228 (0.0231)
Male	0.475	-0.0606* (0.0320)	0.0785*** (0.0170)	-0.0971*** (0.0297)	0.108*** (0.0154)

Age	51.84 (16.862)	0.0171*** (0.00548)	0.00711** (0.00321)	0.0144*** (0.00494)	-0.00656** (0.00316)
Age ² /1000	2.97 (1.776)	-0.310*** (0.0506)	-0.149*** (0.0312)	-0.247*** (0.0452)	0.0398 (0.0311)
Marital status					
Married (<i>reference</i>)	0.601	-	-	-	-
Single	0.216	-0.374*** (0.0543)	-0.138*** (0.0263)	-0.336*** (0.0519)	-0.0372 (0.0243)
Widowed	0.061	-0.277*** (0.0574)	-0.234*** (0.0394)	-0.207*** (0.0467)	-0.151*** (0.0375)
Divorced/separated	0.122	-0.504*** (0.0454)	-0.218*** (0.0261)	-0.430*** (0.0413)	-0.0406* (0.0235)
Household size	2.609 (1.307)	-0.116*** (0.0194)	-0.123*** (0.00982)	-0.0500*** (0.0193)	-0.124*** (0.00958)
Children in household	0.528 (0.936)	0.0675*** (0.0259)	0.122*** (0.0130)	-0.00664 (0.0269)	0.157*** (0.0124)
Years of education	12.593 (2.799)	0.153*** (0.00887)	0.0764*** (0.00323)	0.126*** (0.0104)	0.0427*** (0.00277)
German nationality	0.933	0.279*** (0.0522)	0.103*** (0.0328)	0.228*** (0.0445)	-0.0197 (0.0305)
Log(household income)	5.519 (0.602)	0.702*** (0.0416)	0.406*** (0.0175)	0.508*** (0.0338)	0.244*** (0.0147)
Labour status					
Full time	0.402	0.143*** (0.0451)	-0.151*** (0.0243)	0.222*** (0.0486)	-0.229*** (0.0231)
Part-time	0.265	0.160*** (0.0415)	-0.0161 (0.0235)	0.165*** (0.0374)	-0.0944*** (0.0221)
Not working (<i>reference</i>)	0.332	-	-	-	-
Year of interview					
2013 (<i>reference</i>)	0.422	-	-	-	-
2019	0.578	0.164*** (0.0263)	0.178*** (0.0135)	0.0856*** (0.0241)	0.173*** (0.0130)
<i>Constant</i>	-	-3.679*** (0.330)		-2.835*** (0.309)	
Number of observations		39,866	39,866	39,866	
Mean value (standard deviation)		0.892 (0.310)	1.312 (0.728)	1.312 (0.728)	
Wald X ²		1,207.3	3,359.0	1,961.3	
Log pseudolikelihood		-10,736.1	-40,041.8	-39,728.3	

Note: Note: Individuals aged 15 or over. *** $P < 0.01$, ** $P < 0.05$, * $P < 0.1$. All regressions also include region dummies. Standard errors are clustering per individual. Source: SOEP for years 2013 and 2019.

Appendix

Table A1. Sample distribution of the dependent variable used in each model.

1) RE probit model (Participation versus non-participation)

	Participation in holiday trips		
Disability status:	No (=0)	Yes (=1)	Total
Non-disabled	1,904	24,610	26,514
Moderate limited	1,262	8,421	9,683
Severe limited	1,140	2,529	3,669
Total	4,306	35,560	39,866

2) RE ordered probit model and ZIOP model (Participation and its intensity)

	Intensity of participation in holiday trips				
Disability status:	Never (=0)	Seldom (=1)	At least once a month (=2)	Daily/at least once per week (=3)	Total
Non-disabled	1,904	13,825	9,376	1,409	26,514
Moderate limited	1,262	5,240	2,726	455	9,683
Severe limited	1,140	1,729	680	120	3,669
Total	4,306	20,794	12,782	1,984	39,866

Source: Own elaboration from the SOEP for the years 2013 and 2019.

Table A2. Mean values (M) and standard deviation (SD) of explanatory variables used in Table 2 by disability status.

	Non-disabled		Moderate limited		Severe limited	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Personality traits (Big 5)						
Openness	0.928	0.258	0.870	0.337	0.689	0.463
Conscientiousness	4.623	1.170	4.555	1.212	4.461	1.304
Extraversion	5.848	0.889	5.824	0.912	5.727	1.039
Agreeableness	4.948	1.121	4.812	1.132	4.726	1.190
Neuroticism	5.416	0.950	5.399	0.968	5.405	1.059
Male	0.493	0.500	0.442	0.497	0.434	0.496
Age	47.890	16.032	58.322	15.634	63.248	15.274
Age ² /1000	2.550	1.599	3.646	1.767	4.234	1.870
Marital status						
Married	0.595		0.631		0.567	0.595
Single	0.256		0.144		0.120	0.256
Widowed	0.038		0.088		0.152	0.038
Divorced/separated	0.111		0.137		0.161	0.111
Household size	2.776	1.348	2.344	1.158	2.099	1.109
Children in household	0.637	0.995	0.348	0.796	0.218	0.653
Years of education	12.906	2.855	12.168	2.630	11.454	2.341
German nationality	0.927		0.946		0.945	
Log(household income)	5.584	0.609	5.435	0.573	5.266	0.527
Labour status						
Full time	0.483		0.292		0.111	
Part-time	0.287		0.245		0.168	
Not working	0.231		0.463		0.721	
Year of interview						
2013	0.417		0.418		0.464	
2019	0.583		0.582		0.536	
Region of residence						
Schleswig–Holstein	0.034		0.031		0.039	
Hamburg	0.020		0.016		0.019	
Lower Saxony	0.092		0.104		0.097	
Bremen	0.007		0.008		0.006	
North-Rhine-Westfalia	0.206		0.191		0.209	
Hessen	0.070		0.065		0.061	
Rheinland-Pfalz	0.048		0.047		0.043	
Baden-Wuerttemberg	0.117		0.100		0.095	
Bavaria	0.161		0.145		0.140	
Saarland	0.008		0.009		0.012	
Berlin	0.040		0.043		0.042	
Brandenburg	0.038		0.050		0.060	
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	0.024		0.025		0.026	
Saxony	0.064		0.075		0.065	
Saxony-Anhalt	0.033		0.047		0.041	
Thuringia	0.037		0.043		0.047	
Number of observations	26,514		9,683		3,669	

Source: Own elaboration from the SOEP for the years 2013 and 2019.